

A New Pattern of Molecular Architecture*

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During post war years as the result of a large increase in the number of investigators in the field of natural products and of the improved methods of study, a vast number of new compounds have been isolated and their constitutions established. This has been proceeding at an accelerated rate. There has therefore been an urgent need for classifying the numerous compounds for purposes of study. When closely examined, they tend to fall into certain important patterns, which get well defined when reviewed on the basis of biogenesis. One such pattern has taken rapid shape during the past few years and it is growing bigger as a group. These compounds come under what may be called 4-phenylchroman derivatives. In this line considerable contribution has been made by the study of heartwood extractives, an inquiry of fundamental interest for understanding the causes of the special qualities of well-known and valuable heartwoods, such as their stability to atmospheric conditions and their resistance to attack by insects and micro-organisms.

Discovery of 4-Phenylchroman Derivatives

The earliest members to be discovered were brazilin (I) and haematoxylin (II) and these were known in crystalline condition even during the last century. They were the main components of the well-known dyewoods, brazil wood and log wood respectively, indigenous to South America. Brazilin is also present in the important South Indian dyewood, sappan wood. Their constitutions were established during the first quarter of this century, largely by the work of Porkin and Robinson and their collaborators (for a recent review see Robinson¹). Besides their special structure, they provide interest on account of the various complex transformations they undergo. Discussing their possible biogenesis, Robinson² suggested that brazilin could arise from dihydrobutein by the entry of a single carbon atom. Experimental support was provided for this by the condensation of dihydrobutein trimethyl ether (III) with formic acid in presence of hydrogen chloride and ferric chloride to yield trimethylbrazilium ferric chloride (IV)³ which could also be obtained from brazilin through trimethylbrazilcin (V) as an important intermediate. This would suggest that brazilin and haematoxylin are related to normal flavonoids which are 2-phenylchroman derivatives. In his well-known lectures⁴ published in 1955 he made the remark that though brazilin and haematoxylin had in them a 4-phenylchroman skeleton, a simple member of this group had not so far been isolated. Therefore there was a general

*Substance of the Presidential Address delivered at the 40th Annual General Meeting of the Indian Chemical Society in Calcutta on 18th January, 1963.

1. Robinson, *Bull. Soc. Chim.*, 1958, 125.

2. Robinson, "The Structural Relations of Natural Products", 1955, p. 42, Clarendon Press,

3. Cradtree and Robinson, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1918, 859.

tendency to consider that brazilin and haematoxylin were derived from 2-phenylchromans. The position has now been considerably changed. About twelve compounds are already known which are definitely either 4-phenylcoumarins or have a closely related carbon skeleton. Consequently there is now adequate support for the proposal⁴ made in 1957, that these compounds represent a new pattern arising from a different mode of linking of C₆ and C₉ units.

(I: R = H).

(II: R = OH).

4-Phenylcoumarins

The first few members of the new group to be discovered came under the category of 4-phenylcoumarins. The simplest is dalbergin isolated from the heartwood of *Dalbergia sissoo*, a timber tree, very common in North India. It is accompanied by lesser quantities of its methyl ether, called methylalbergin⁵.

Dalbergin is a hydroxy compound having the molecular formula C₁₆H₁₂O₄ with one hydroxyl group and one methoxyl group and lactonic properties. On methylation it yielded methylalbergin which could be partially demethylated to dalbergin. The methyl ether was considerably stable towards alkali and gave marked colour with magnesium and hydrochloric acid (emerald-green changing to deep red). These were reminiscent of the behaviour of normal flavonoids. But it underwent ready oxidation with neutral perman-

⁴ Seshadri, *Curr. Sci.*, 1957, 26, 240.

⁵ Ahluwalia and Seshadri, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1957, 970.

ganate to yield benzoic acid, oxalic acid, and 2-hydroxy-4,5-dimethoxybenzophenone. Further, the I. R. spectrum indicated an unsaturated lactone structure. *O*-Methylalbergin was therefore considered to be 6,7-dimethoxy-4-phenylcoumarin (VI) and this was confirmed by synthesis involving methylation of 4-phenylaesuletin. Dalbergin was shown to be 6-hydroxy-7-methoxy-4-phenylcoumarin (VII) by synthesis, following unambiguous methods^{6,7}. A special feature of methylalbergin is that on boiling with aqueous alkali and mercuric oxide, it undergoes conversion into the corresponding 3-phenylcoumarilic acid (VIII), a change involving geometrical inversion, followed by ring closure and oxidation⁸.

(VI: R = Me)

(VII: R = H)

(VIII)

A group of three compounds has been isolated from the seeds of the tropical plant, *Calophyllum inophyllum*: calophyllolide, inophyllolide, and calophyllilic acid.⁹ Of these, calophyllolide is the major component and most important, since it is found to have valuable therapeutic properties. Originally it was considered to be useful against leprosy. More recently it is found to be efficient as a blood-anticoagulant. Alkali degradation has been more fruitful in the study of the structure of this group and this seems to be due to presence of an acyl group in the 8-position of the coumarin structure. The constitution of calophyllolide was established by two main degradative reactions. Alkaline degradation of calophyllolide (IX) yielded 5-hydroxy-7-methoxy-4-phenylcoumarin besides acetophenone, acetaldehyde, propionic acid, and acetone, thereby establishing that it is a 4-phenylcoumarin derivative having a 2,2-dimethylchromene unit and an α -methylecrotonyl grouping.

(IX)

(X)

(XI)

6. Ahluwalia, Mehta, and Beshadri, *Proc. Ind. Acad. Sci.*, 1957, A45, 16.

7. *Idem, ibid.*, 1957, A45, 293.

8. *Idem, Tetrahedron*, 1958, 4, 271.

9. Polunsky, *Bull. Soc. Chim.*, 1957, 1079.

Further confirmation of these conclusions was provided by a study of the action of hydriodic acid and phosphorus on calophyllolide which yielded a number of products whose constitutions could be established. Demethylation of calophyllolide is accompanied by ring closure and the products are inophyllolide (X) and calophyllic acid (XI) which are inter-convertible. The stability of calophyllic acid is of particular significance and this could be attributed to the presence of the carboxyl group *ortho* to the phenolic hydroxyl.

From the fruit pulp of *Mammea americana*, an insecticidal plant, indigenous to Mexico, two components have been obtained, one of which, mammeisin, is a 4-phenylcoumarin¹⁰. The constitution of mammeisin (XII) could be arrived at in the following manner. Prolonged boiling with 15% alkali yielded three products which were identified as isovaleric acid, acetophenone, and isopentenylphloroglucinol. The dihydro derivative of mammeisin underwent deacylation with 75% sulphuric acid to furnish 5,7-dihydroxy-8-isopentyl-4-phenylcoumarin, the constitution of which was established by synthesis. Recently another 4-phenylcoumarin, mesuol (XIII), has been isolated from *Mesua ferrea*¹¹. The details of its constitution are, however, not yet available. It seems to be an unusual example having an allyl (C₃) unit instead of the isoprene (C₅) unit as a nuclear substituent in the 6-position.

(XII)

(XIII)

Latifolin Group

All the above seven compounds belong to the 4-phenylcoumarin group. The existence of other types having the same pattern of C₁₅ skeleton has been discovered by a more recent study. This work relates to the chemistry of the heartwood components of *Dalbergia latifolia*, which is a very valuable timber tree found in South India and is commonly called Indian Rosewood or Blackwood. When fresh, it is milder in colour, but it develops a deep black colour and hardens more and more as it ages. Obviously deep seated chemical changes are involved. Light petroleum extracts from this heartwood a considerable amount of a coloured material. However, on concentration the extract yields a colorless crystalline compound, m. p. 122-23°, having the molecular composition C₁₇H₁₆O₄. This is found to be new and hence has been given the name *latifolin*¹². Recently two nitrogenous compounds—one isolated from the plant *Cynoglossum latifolium* having the molecular composition C₂₁H₂₇O₇N and found to be an ester of 7-angelyl retroncine¹³ and the other

10. Finnegan and Djerassi, *Tetrahedron Letters*, 1959, No. 13, 11.

11. Chakraborty and Bose, *Proc. Nat. Acad. Sci., India*, 1960, A26, supplement I, 1.

12. Balakrishna, Rao, and Seshadri, *Tetrahedron*, 1962, 18, 1503.

13. Chrowley and Culvenor, *Austral. J. Chem.*, 1962, 15, 139.

that one of them is adjacent to one oxygen, whereas the other is adjacent to two. Hence it is concluded that these two protons are *para* to each other on a tetra-substituted benzene ring with 2,4,6-oxygeation pattern. The splitting pattern between τ 2.6 and 3.5 P. P. M. is typical of those in a 1,2,3,4-situation on a di-substituted benzene ring (B). The positions of the signals of the olefinic protons and the proton on the carbon holding the two phenyl rings and also their coupling constants are as expected for the structure of latifolin dimethyl ether given above (XV).

As already mentioned, chromic acid oxidation of *O*-dimethyl-latifolin yielded a yellow quinone. It had the molecular formula $C_{17}H_{16}O_4$ with only two methoxyls. Obviously this was a case of oxidative demethylation where two *para* methoxyls had undergone conversion to a quinone structure. Its structural formula can therefore be represented as in (XVIII) and this has been fully supported by its elemental analysis and U. V., I. R., and N. M. R. spectra. A characteristic property of this substance, called *latifolinone*, is the formation of a blue colour with ethanolic alkali.

In extracting the remaining components of the heartwood of *D. latifolia*, acetone extraction was found to be quite satisfactory. Most of the extract was soluble in ethyl acetate and the ethyl acetate solution was subjected to column chromatography on neutral alumina. Fractional elution yielded four crystalline components of which latifolin was one. Another was a yellow crystalline compound which resembled latifolinone closely in colour reactions and spectra. It had the molecular composition $C_{16}H_{14}O_3$ with one methoxyl. The location of this methoxyl in the quinone part was clear when the compound on oxidation with alkaline permanganate yielded benzoic acid. Therefore it is a lower member of latifolinone type having the structural formula (XIX) and has been named *dalberginone*, since it is closely related to dalbergin, is an ethylene and a quinone¹⁵. This structure is in agreement with its N. M. R. spectrum which gave signals for the following: one methoxyl (τ 6.17, 3 protons), 5-aromatic protons (τ 2.70), two signals at 4.05 and 3.50 attributable to the two protons on the quinone unit. The sharp singlet at τ 4.05 is due to a proton which is between two oxygen atoms. The signal at 3.50 could be assigned to proton H(1) and its splitting indicated the presence of a proton in the allylic position nearby.

About the same time as our work, Eyton, Ollis, Sutherland, Jackman, Gottlieb, and Magalhães have been examining the components of the heartwood of *Dalbergia nigra* and they recently reported¹⁶ isolation of dalberginone, which they have called dalbergione.

15. Rao and Seshadri, *Tetrahedron Letters*, under publication.

16. Eyton *et al.*, *Proc. Chem. Soc.*, 1962, 301.

along with its 4'-hydroxy (XX) and 4'-methoxy (XXI) derivatives. They have studied their chemical and spectral properties and have also established their stereochemistry. They effected the synthesis of dalbergione in the following way: Resorcinol monomethyl ether and cinnamyl bromide gave the corresponding ether. This ether was rearranged thermally to the phenol which by oxidation with Fremy's salt gave racemic dalbergione.

(XVIII)

(XIX: R = H)
 (XX: R = OH)
 (XXI: R = OMe)

Biogenesis

The isolation of the above new components from *D. latifolia* and similar compounds from *D. nigra* is of interest for the study of biogenesis since they all have the C_{15} skeleton, characteristic of 4-phenylchromans, and the new variations provide fresh and useful information.

A very large number of polyphenolic compounds occur in Nature having the C_{15} skeleton. This skeleton is definitely composed of two distinct units, C_9 and C_6 . The majority of known C_{15} compounds are derived from 2-phenylchromans or normal flavans. The C_6 unit in them is considered to arise by the combination of three C_2 (acetate) units and the other (the C_9 unit) is evolved from shikimic acid through the intermediate stages of phenylalanine or cinnamic acid derivatives. A less number of compounds are derivatives of 5-phenylchromans or isoflavans. These are related to the normal flavans and involve migration of the side phenyl nucleus. This is considered to take place in the chalkone stage of evolution and has been proved by tracer technique^{17,18}. A synthesis modelled on this scheme has also been recently adopted in a convenient laboratory synthesis of isoflavones¹⁹.

Still smaller in number are 4-phenylchroman derivatives. Besides brazilin and haematoxylin, known even from the last century, seven 4-phenylcoumarins (having the 4-phenylchroman group) have been added to this group during the past six years. Discussing the biosynthesis of dalbergin and its analogues, it was originally suggested⁴ that the formation of this skeleton also involved the same C_9 and C_6 units as found in flavonoids, but these are linked at the α -carbon atom of the C_9 unit, whereas in the normal flavonoids

17. Grisebeck and Brandner, *Exper.*, 1962, 18, 400.

18. Idem, *Biochim. Biophys. Acta*, 1962, 60, 51.

19. Grover, Jain, and Seshadri, under publication.

the linking is at the γ -carbon atom. As laboratory analogy, the reaction of resorcinol (XXII) with cinnamic acid to yield 4-phenyldihydroumbelliferone²⁰ (XXIII) and with benzoylacetic ester to yield the 4-phenylumbelliferone²¹ (XXIV) itself may be mentioned. The above scheme is applicable to all the 4-phenylcoumarins except that in several of the members isoprene and other groups are substituted in nuclear positions (see calophylloide, IX). The latest compounds discovered in *Dalbergia* woods as represented by latifolin, dalbergenone (XIX) and its 4'-hydroxy (XX) and 4'-methoxy (XXI) analogues have this carbon skeleton, but the middle ring is not closed. Their structures, however, support the mode of linking of the two units C_6 and C_9 as mentioned above. Even in this construction there are two possibilities. The hydroxyquinol part represents the C_6 unit and the C_9 is represented by the unsubstituted or mono-substituted allylbenzene part or *vice versa*. The former possibility seems, however, to be more correct, based on considerations of substitution patterns. Brazilin and haematoxylin represent a more complex type, incorporating a single carbon atom in an undetermined way.

It was earlier pointed out² that naturally occurring benzophenones could be derived by oxidation of the 4-phenylcoumarins or better the corresponding cinnamic acids. Therefore these ketones could also be added to the 4-phenylchroman group as derived compounds. They may be more easily derived from latifolin group of compounds by similar oxidations as indicated below.

20. Simpson and Stephen, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1956, 1382.

21. Von Pechmann *et al.*, *Ber.*, 1883, 16, 2126.